

PRAGMALINGUISTIC CATEGORIES OF CHOICE AND SPEECH ACTIVITIES

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Abstract: The purpose of this article is due to the increased interest modern linguistics to the study of language in close connection with the practical human activity. Research interest in discourse is also due to the global nature of pragmalinguistics, which is encountered in the context of social communications

Key words: pragmalinguistics, categories, semantics, linguistic study, communicants

As one of the leading categories of pragmalinguistics, the category of choice allows you to delimit the aspect of pragmalinguistics from the aspects of semantics and syntax. When analyzing a text, the criterion of the semantic aspect is the adequacy of the linguistic unit of objective reality; criterion syntactic aspect is the correctness of the organization of language units at all levels of the language; the criterion of the pragmatic aspect is successful use of language units by the sender of the text for optimal impact on its recipient. It is the introduction to linguistic study of function dependency linguistic units from such extralinguistic factors as communicants, led to a paradigm shift in research in linguistics: from studying language in itself as a system of pure relations, linguists turned to the study of the functioning of the language in the conditions of extralinguistic reality.

The speaker's choice of the optimal variant of the statement is determined by number of factors, which, in addition to the goal and motive, include the situation communicants with their social and psychological personal qualities. Speech pragmalinguistic influencing methods achievement of the same goal is diverse. In particular, it may be the choice illocutions of a request, illocutions of advice, illocutions of an order, illocutions statements. Achievement of the goal occurs through the choice of statements, constructed according to different syntactic models - interrogative, imperative, declarative sentence. Also varied lexical completion of model components. Within the framework of functional pragmalinguistics, within which lies our research, is studied purposeful, motivated, intentional choice of linguistic units (lexemes and syntactic structures). from a set of equivalent ones to achieve the optimal impact on the recipient of the text.

As already noted, from the standpoint of pragmalinguistics, interest represents the pragmatic success of the utterance. In order to to make a good choice, one must be able to perform two operations - to combine dissimilar (combination) and separate the equivalent (selection).

Selection, or choice, is made on the basis of equivalence, similarity, and also on the basis of difference, synonymy, antonymy. Combination based on adjacency, for example, when constructing a sentence. To external extralinguistic subjective limitations social characteristics of the conditions for the implementation of speech act to ensure its influencing function, in particular, components of a speech act - the sender of the text, its recipient, message, context, code, contact.

To intralinguistic objective restrictions on the choice of linguistic units include accounting speaking / writing language patterns of language organization for implementation of the information function - language systems in general, level properties of language units:

phonetic, lexical, including word structures, word combinations, sentences, including the order of the elements, text. The choice of speakers / writers is systemically unlimited and limited functionally, stylistically, contextually and situationally.

To social determinants that limit freedom of choice communicant of linguistic units include age, profession, social status, gender, etc. All these social determinants are stored in the memory and knowledge of communicants and make them presuppositions, or background knowledge. So the choice seen as a preference for speaking writers in the population possible options for uttering those of them that correspond to his communicative goals and intentions, as well as intralinguistic and extralinguistic conditions of verbal communication to achieve optimal impact on the recipient of the text.

Speech activity in psychology is considered as one of the types human activity along with labor, cognitive, play, etc . Speech activity has three aspects: motivational, target and executive. Speech activity is born out of need. Further, using signs, activity is planned, it is put the end goal and the means to achieve it. By implementing activity, we reach the final goal. Single act of activity manifests itself in the unity of all three sides.

In linguistics, the definition of speech activity was first given L.V. Shcherboy, who advocated a threefold approach to language and as aspects of the language distinguished between speech activity, the language system (dictionary and grammar of the language), linguistic material (the totality of everything spoken and understood in a given context). Associated with this definition common in the methodology of foreign languages, the concept of "types of speech activities, including speaking, listening, reading and writing.

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